

SCIENTIFIC PAPER WRITING TRAINING FOR STATE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN DUKUH KUPANG V DUKUH PAKIS DISTRICT, SURABAYA

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ABSTRACT

Scientific writing training has a aims to (1) increase the motivation of teachers in SDN Dukuh Kupang V Surabaya for writing scientific papers and (2) improve the ability of teachers in SDN Dukuh Kupang V Surabaya for writing scientific papers in the form of a research report. Achievement of these goals is done through training with lectures, question and answer, demonstration, and practice (tutorials). After the training activities carried out monitoring or evaluation by the organizing committee to see and assist teachers in writing scientific papers. Hasi research shows that that P2M program is going well and smoothly. The program is able to provide motivation for teachers in writing scientific papers and is able to improve the ability of teachers to conduct research and write a research report. Constraints that arise at the stage of research and the writing of the results of the research can be overcome with the assistance methods. Suggestions that can be submitted from the results of the extension program, elementary school teachers are expected to have motivation and always cultivate scientific writing activities. Education practitioners are expected to always be able to help elementary school teachers in scientific writing activities

Keywords: *Writing Scientific Papers, Elementary School Teachers, District Dukuh Pakis V*

I. INTRODUCTION

The position of a teacher as an educator is a professional position. This is stated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System. In other words, teachers are required to be able to carry out their duties professionally. A person is considered professional if he can carry out his duties by always adhering to work ethics, independently (free from external pressure), quickly (productively) precisely (effectively), efficiently and innovatively, and based on the principles of excellent service based on elements of systematic science or theory, professional authority, public recognition, and a regulatory code of ethics.

Government regulations on the development of the teaching profession have long been established, namely in the Decree of the Minister of State for Empowerment

of State Apparatus Number 84 of 1993 dated December 24, 1993. The ministerial decree describes the fields of teacher activities consisting of main elements and supporting elements. The main elements include the fields of education, teaching and learning processes, and development. profession,

The purpose of teacher professional development activities is to improve the quality of teachers so that they are more professional in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. So, the activity aims to increase the number of professional teachers, not to accelerate or slow down the increase in rank or class. Furthermore, as an appreciation for teachers who can increase their professionalism. One of the efforts to increase professionalism that is also related to efforts to increase rank is writing scientific papers. Writing scientific papers is often a difficult activity for teachers to do. It has been explained previously that one way to increase professionalism is through writing scientific papers. Other ways that can be taken are by (1) finding technology in the field of education, (2) making teaching tools/teaching tools or guidance tools, and (3) participating in curriculum development activities (Ministry of National Education, 2001:1). Of these methods, writing scientific papers for most teachers including elementary school teachers is an activity that is still difficult to do so that a lot of guidance is needed (Sumardi, 2011).

In general, many teachers still have difficulty in increasing rank and class from IV a/coaching to IV b / Level I Coach and above, the obstacle is the creation of written scientific papers which are required to meet a minimum credit score of 12 from the professional development decline which includes carrying out written work or scientific work activities in the field of education. Lately, difficulties have been increasingly felt by teachers with lower ranks with the Ministerial Decree No. 16 of 2009 concerning scientific papers which have become a requirement for promotion from group III b to III c. Therefore, scientific paper writing training for teachers, especially elementary school teachers, is needed. From the results of discussions with elementary school teachers in groups III b and IV a in Dukuh Pakis District, Buleleng Regency, it is clear that many elementary school teachers experience obstacles in writing scientific papers, especially in the form of research reports. Therefore, this scientific paper writing training will be aimed at teachers at SDN Dukuh Kupang V Surabaya.

The anxiety experienced by elementary school teachers in writing scientific papers is the lack of time to write. In addition to teaching hours, this anxiety is also caused by the inability of teachers to divide their time between teaching and looking for references as research materials. Although writing scientific papers is included in one of the requirements for promotion, teachers' interest and motivation in writing scientific papers is still low. Scientific papers are seen as something difficult to do or create. Teachers tend to label themselves as incapable of doing it. A teacher can write a scientific paper well, only the will is the obstacle. Therefore, counseling on writing scientific papers is carried out to motivate teachers to create their scientific papers.

The aim of the scientific paper writing training for State Elementary School teachers at SDN Dukuh Kupang V is to equip these educators with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively produce high-quality scientific papers, particularly

research reports, which are essential for their professional development and career advancement. This training is designed to address the specific challenges that elementary school teachers face in meeting the requirements for rank and class progression, thereby enabling them to fulfill the mandatory credit score requirements for promotion and enhancing their overall competence in the field of education.

II. METHODOLOGY

This community service activity aims to improve the motivation and ability to write scientific papers for elementary school teachers in Dukuh Pakis District, Surabaya. The following materials are provided in the training:

1. Techniques for identifying, selecting, and formulating topics/titles of scientific papers.
2. Techniques for compiling a framework for writing scientific papers.
3. Techniques for collecting materials, organizing, and conceptualizing scientific papers.
4. Techniques for writing and editing scientific papers

The target of this community service is elementary school teachers at SDN Dukuh Kupang V Surabaya. This target is intended for 24 people. This scientific paper writing training activity is carried out through semi-formal discussions. This makes teachers not feel lectured which makes the atmosphere unpleasant, but rather becomes a discussion session by exchanging opinions. The following learning methods are used to support the success of the training:

1. Lecture and Q&A. This method was chosen to raise teachers' motivation in writing scientific papers and explain theoretical material related to laws and regulations concerning promotion and credit points. In addition, it also discusses various scientific papers including classroom action research reports.
2. Demonstration. This method is chosen to explain a work process in stages so that it can make it easier for participants to carefully observe the process of making scientific papers from preparation to editing the manuscript.
3. Exercise/Practice or tutorial. In this method, participants practice making scientific papers with training guidance so that participants can make scientific papers well. To find out the success of this activity is done by looking at the enthusiasm of the participants during the training and a questionnaire to collect data on teacher responses to the implementation of the training.

III. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The position of a teacher as an educator in Indonesia is recognized as a professional role, as outlined in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System. This law underscores the critical responsibility that teachers hold in shaping the educational landscape. It emphasizes that teachers are not merely facilitators of learning but are professionals who must adhere to a high standard of conduct, underpinned by a deep understanding of

pedagogical theory and practice. To be considered professional, teachers must demonstrate a commitment to ethical work principles. This means that teachers are expected to perform their duties with integrity, adhering to a strict code of ethics that governs their behavior and decision-making processes. Such adherence ensures that their actions are always in the best interest of their students and the broader educational goals. Ethical behavior in this context includes fairness, honesty, and respect for the diversity and individuality of students.

Moreover, professionalism in teaching also requires independence. Teachers must be able to perform their duties free from external pressures or influences that could compromise their judgment or effectiveness. This independence allows teachers to focus on delivering education that is true to the curriculum and responsive to the needs of their students without undue interference from non-educational stakeholders. Efficiency and innovation are also key aspects of professionalism in teaching. A professional teacher is not only expected to deliver lessons effectively and efficiently but also to be productive in their role. This includes the ability to manage time well, use resources wisely, and deliver educational outcomes in a manner that maximizes learning while minimizing waste. Furthermore, teachers are encouraged to be innovative, constantly seeking new and better ways to engage students and improve their learning experiences. Innovation in education could involve integrating new technologies, adopting novel teaching methodologies, or finding creative solutions to common classroom challenges.

Finally, professionalism in teaching is built on a foundation of systematic science or theory, professional authority, public recognition, and adherence to a regulatory code of ethics. This means that teachers are expected to base their practices on established educational theories and research, which provides a sound and reliable foundation for their work. They must also possess the professional authority to make decisions in the classroom and be recognized by society as competent and capable educators. Public recognition, in this context, refers to the trust and respect that teachers earn from their students, parents, and the community at large. Adhering to a regulatory code of ethics ensures that teachers' actions are consistent with the values and standards of the profession, further reinforcing their status as professionals.

The development of the teaching profession in Indonesia has been a focus of government regulation for several decades. One of the key regulations in this regard is the Decree of the Minister of State for Empowerment of State Apparatus Number 84 of 1993, issued on December 24, 1993. This decree outlines the various fields of activities that are integral to the teaching profession, categorizing them into main elements and supporting elements. The main elements, as described in the decree, encompass critical aspects of a teacher's professional responsibilities. These include the fields of education, the teaching and learning process, and professional development. In the field of education, teachers are expected to contribute to the broader educational system, shaping the curriculum and ensuring that educational standards are met. This responsibility extends beyond the classroom and includes

participation in educational planning, policy implementation, and collaboration with other educators to enhance the overall quality of education.

The teaching and learning process is another primary element emphasized in the decree. Teachers are at the forefront of facilitating student learning, which involves not only delivering content but also creating an engaging and supportive learning environment. This process requires teachers to employ effective teaching strategies, assess student progress, and adapt their methods to meet the diverse needs of their students. The goal is to ensure that every student can achieve their full potential through a well-structured and dynamic educational experience. Professional development is the third main element highlighted in the decree. It recognizes that teaching is an evolving profession that requires continuous learning and growth. Teachers are encouraged to engage in ongoing professional development activities, such as attending workshops, pursuing further education, and staying updated with the latest educational research and technologies. This commitment to lifelong learning helps teachers to refine their skills, adopt new teaching practices, and maintain their professional competence.

The Decree of the Minister of State for Empowerment of State Apparatus Number 84 of 1993 establishes a comprehensive framework for the teaching profession in Indonesia. By defining the main elements of teacher activities—education, the teaching and learning process, and professional development—the decree ensures that teachers are well-equipped to fulfill their roles effectively and contribute to the advancement of education in the country. The professional development of teachers is a critical aspect of enhancing the overall quality of education. The primary purpose of these activities is to ensure that teachers are more skilled, knowledgeable, and effective in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Professional development is not merely a mechanism for accelerating or decelerating the process of promotion or rank advancement; rather, it is focused on fostering genuine professional growth. By engaging in these activities, teachers can become more adept at their work, ultimately benefiting their students and the educational system as a whole.

One significant aspect of teacher professional development is the recognition and appreciation of those who can successfully enhance their professionalism. Among the various methods available for increasing professionalism, writing scientific papers stands out as both a valuable and challenging endeavor. Writing scientific papers requires teachers to engage in deep reflection, critical analysis, and the synthesis of knowledge, which are all essential skills for professional growth. However, despite its importance, writing scientific papers is often seen as a daunting task, particularly for teachers who may not have received sufficient training or support in this area.

Beyond writing scientific papers, there are other effective ways to enhance teacher professionalism. These include discovering or integrating new technology in the field of education, developing innovative teaching tools or guidance instruments, and actively participating in curriculum development activities. Each of these

methods contributes to a teacher's professional development by encouraging creativity, innovation, and a deeper understanding of educational practices.

For many teachers, especially those at the elementary school level, writing scientific papers remains a particularly challenging activity. This difficulty often stems from a lack of experience, confidence, or access to appropriate guidance and resources. As a result, there is a significant need for targeted support and training to help teachers develop the skills necessary to write scientific papers effectively. Providing this support can help demystify the process of academic writing and enable more teachers to contribute to the body of educational research, thereby enhancing their professionalism and potentially impacting their career progression. While writing scientific papers is a crucial element of teacher professional development, it is important to recognize that it is just one of several ways to foster professionalism. Efforts to increase teacher professionalism should be multifaceted, providing teachers with the tools, resources, and support they need to succeed in various aspects of their professional lives. With the right guidance and opportunities, teachers can overcome the challenges associated with writing scientific papers and fully embrace the broader goals of professional development.

The challenge of advancing in rank and class is a significant issue faced by many teachers, particularly when moving from rank IV a (Coaching) to IV b (Level I Coach) and higher. One of the primary obstacles in this progression is the requirement to produce written scientific papers, which are necessary to accumulate a minimum credit score of 12 from professional development activities. These activities, as outlined by various educational regulations, include the creation and publication of scientific work in the field of education. The difficulties associated with writing scientific papers have become even more pronounced with the implementation of Ministerial Decree No. 16 of 2009. This decree has established that scientific papers are a mandatory requirement for teachers seeking promotion from group III b to III c. As a result, many teachers, particularly those in lower ranks, find themselves struggling to meet these requirements due to the challenges associated with academic writing. This is especially true for elementary school teachers, who may have less experience with research and scientific writing compared to their peers at higher educational levels.

In light of these challenges, there is a growing recognition of the need for targeted training programs to help teachers improve their skills in writing scientific papers. Such training is particularly crucial for elementary school teachers, who often face unique difficulties in this area. For example, discussions with teachers in groups III b and IV a in Dukuh Pakis District, Buleleng Regency, revealed that many elementary school teachers struggle with writing scientific papers, particularly research reports. These teachers often lack the necessary experience, guidance, and confidence to produce the high-quality scientific work required for promotion. Given this context, it is clear that scientific paper writing training is essential to support teachers in overcoming these challenges. The proposed training will specifically target teachers at SDN Dukuh Kupang V in Surabaya. By focusing on this group, the training aims to equip these teachers with the skills and knowledge needed to write

effective scientific papers, thereby enabling them to meet the requirements for rank advancement. The training will likely include practical guidance on research methodologies, writing techniques, and the structure of scientific papers, all tailored to the needs of elementary school teachers. The need for scientific paper writing training for teachers, particularly those at the elementary level, is critical. Such training will not only help teachers overcome the barriers to rank advancement but also contribute to their overall professional development, ultimately enhancing the quality of education they provide.

Optimizing Teacher Development Through Holiday Training: A Case Study at SDN Dukuh Kupang V Surabaya

The implementation of the training activity was strategically planned over two days, which coincided with school holidays. This scheduling decision was made to ensure that the training did not interfere with the regular teaching and learning hours, allowing the teachers to fully engage in the sessions without any distractions or conflicts with their primary responsibilities. The training was organized by the school, with coordination between the principal and the teachers of SDN Dukuh Kupang V Surabaya, demonstrating a collaborative effort to enhance the professional development of the educators.

The teachers displayed a high level of enthusiasm for the training, indicating their eagerness to improve their skills and knowledge. However, the enthusiasm was somewhat tempered by the challenges posed by the unequal distribution of online access, which was necessary because the training was conducted virtually. On Monday, Tuesday, and Wednesday, the training schedule was divided between lower-grade teachers (grades 1, 2, and 3) who participated from the school, and higher-grade teachers (grades 4, 5, and 6) who joined the sessions from home. This arrangement was made to accommodate the varying circumstances of the teachers, some of whom lived outside of Surabaya. For those residing within the city, conducting research or continuing their professional duties after teaching hours would have been feasible. However, to address the needs of those living further away, it was decided that the training should be held during the school holidays.

On the first day of the training, June 22, 2022, the focus was primarily on research activities. The day included a series of material presentations, discussion sessions, and the drafting of scientific papers. The classroom environment during the presentations was highly conducive to learning, with participants actively engaged in absorbing the material. The discussion and Q&A sessions, while informative, were intentionally designed to be semi-formal. This approach, which included light-hearted jokes, helped to maintain a lively and engaging atmosphere, preventing the sessions from becoming monotonous.

During the draft writing session, some challenges arose, particularly related to misunderstandings of the Indonesian language. Common issues included the use of non-standard words and frequent spelling errors. Despite these hurdles, the teachers persevered in drafting their research papers. The work that was initiated on the first day was continued at home the following day, allowing the participants to

refine their drafts into complete scientific papers. These papers were then ready to be presented and further discussed during the second day of the meeting. This approach ensured that the teachers not only received theoretical knowledge but also had practical opportunities to apply what they learned, resulting in a tangible output in the form of scientific papers.

The second day (June 24, 2022) was the day when the scientific works written by the teachers were discussed together. Based on several scientific works produced by the teachers, not all of them showed success. Some were not appropriate, for example in terms of writing a list of references which was still not congruent with the citations listed in the writing. Several things are worth discussing from the results of the research that has been carried out. The first is related to teacher motivation, teacher motivation which was initially considered lacking in writing scientific papers can be raised by the resource person after being given descriptions of the important role of scientific writing activities for teachers. The enthusiasm of the teachers was increasingly apparent when the relationship between promotion and scientific writing culture was mentioned.

The second thing that needs to be discussed is the enthusiasm of teachers to participate in the training. After providing motivation, the teachers looked enthusiastic in listening and discussing. The resource person and teachers shared their experiences regarding writing scientific papers. After the interview, this enthusiasm was caused by various reasons, such as the desire of teachers to improve their professionalism, especially in conducting classroom action research, the desire to be able to write proposals and research results, and the most common reason was the desire to prepare themselves to be able to move up in class/rank. However, there was a little disappointment from the teachers because this scientific paper writing activity was only carried out for two days. Teachers wanted to get intensive guidance, especially in choosing topics and methods for writing scientific papers.

Third, the thing that needs attention is the obstacles experienced by teachers during the training session to identify problems in the training on classroom action research. The teachers seemed to have difficulty identifying the problems they had. However, because the training was semi-formal, the teachers were not embarrassed to ask each other questions and exchange ideas with jokes. The teachers looked very enthusiastic and shared the problems they had and the solution designs offered to overcome these problems. The teachers then tried to compile a draft of the classroom action research proposal which was continued with the writing of the PTK the following day and ended with a discussion of the PK at the second meeting.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The conclusions that can be drawn after the implementation of this scientific paper writing training are as follows.

1. The activity went well and smoothly.
2. The activity can motivate teachers to create their scientific papers
3. The activity can improve teachers' ability to write scientific papers which include:

- 1) the ability to identify, choose, and formulate topics and titles
- 2) the ability to compile a writing framework (outline)
- 3) the ability to collect writing materials, organize, and conceptualize writing.
- 4) the ability to write and edit scientific papers

This training activity can increase teachers' motivation to write scientific papers. This research activity is also able to improve the understanding of elementary school teachers in Dukuh Pakis District about writing scientific papers. Teachers have the enthusiasm to conduct classroom action research and write it in the form of a research report.

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